
Age distribution Austria vs. Vienna

A Data Management Plan created using DMPonline

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Project abstract:

This experiment compares the age distribution of the population of Austria and Vienna. The data comes from two open data repositories data.europa.eu and data.gv.at.

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Age distribution Austria vs. Vienna - Detailed DMP

1. Data summary

State the purpose of the data collection/generation

The purpose of the data collection was to analyze the differences between the age distribution of Austria and those of Vienna. The analyze has been made for an exercise for the lecture Data Stewardship of the TU Vienna. Bothe dataset were gathered from open data repositories.

Explain the relation to the objectives of the project

The objectives for gathering the data are basically the same as for the project itself, namely producing an experiment for the lecture data stewardship.

Specify the types and formats of data generated/collected

Collected Data: Data about Vienna are provided as multiple csv files. The dataset from Europe as a tsv file. In my experiment I output the raw data as csv file and additionally the plots as png images. All formats are very convenient because csv, tsv and png files are common file formats.

I decided to output my results as csv and png files, because collaboration, long-term preservation and re-use should be no problem with it, they are simple and widely used formats which are standardized.

Specify if existing data is being re-used (if any)

The input Data "Katalog Reginalisierte Bevölkerungsprognose" and "Population by age group" are both reused data.

"Katalog Reginalisierte Bevölkerungsprognose": is the data about Vienna and from the Magistrate of Vienna, published on <https://www.data.gv.at/katalog/dataset/a8ae184c-32e5-4555-82a2-fca5c0e41349> .

"Population by age group": contains data about all European Countries for this project only the data for Austria is used. It's published from Eurostat at <https://data.europa.eu/euodp/en/data/dataset/WUhuriZldIxgoxTJICVELw> .

Both datasets are published under a reusable license.

Specify the origin of the data

"Katalog Reginalisierte Bevölkerungsprognose" is from data.gv.at an open data repository.

"Population by age group" is originally from data.europa.eu

State the expected size of the data (if known)

The total input data of both data sets has around 1.6 MB.

The output data consists of multiple csv files and multiple png figures. Showing the single steps of the data processing till the end result. In total the csv files produced have 10 KB and the figures 76 KB.

Because of the small amount of data storing and processing is possible without any further costs or expected problems.

Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful

The produced data might be useful for people interested in the population of people, it can help to answer the question who is living in the city and who on the

country. (If we might think that more families living on the countryside)

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata [FAIR data]

Outline the discoverability of data (metadata provision)

The whole experiment is published on GitHub (https://github.com/schmidii/data_experiment) and wit DOI's (10.5281/zenodo.2619280,10.5281/zenodo.2617382,10.5281/zenodo.2617376).

In the folder description on GitHub there are additional information about the plots also containing a xml file with the metadata.

Outline the identifiability of data and refer to standard identification mechanism. Do you make use of persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers?

In the project I make use of DOI's (10.5281/zenodo.2619280,10.5281/zenodo.2617382,10.5281/zenodo.2617376). They are assigned for the source code, the DMPs after finishing them and the output results of the project.

Outline naming conventions used

- * `data/raw` - Folder containing the external data
- * `data/processed` - Folder to store the results
- * `reports` - Folder to store the diagrams

Additionally there exists a readme, in Git, describing everything.

Outline the approach towards search keyword

To find the DOI's they got assigned the keywords Vienna, Austria and Population distributed by age. The data also got linked with my OCRID.

To make the project reusable I provided a Readme with instruction how to reproduce the results, as well as a docker file. As mentioned a both in the git there is a folder reports which should help with interpreting the results as well as providing meta data.

Outline the approach for clear versioning

For a clear versioning Git is used. The Results have been tagged with a version number starting with 1, the current and final release has been 1.2.

Specify standards for metadata creation (if any). If there are no standards in your discipline describe what metadata will be created and how

2.2 Making data openly accessible [FAIR data]

Specify which data will be made openly available? If some data is kept closed provide rationale for doing so

The input data is published by other institutions as openly available therefore I don't have to care about it.

The results produced by my experiment will be published under cc-by-4.0 license, so it is also possible to access and use it. There are no data with privacy concerns or something like that therefore the whole data will be published.

Specify how the data will be made available

The data produced has been made public available, with GitHub and DOI's(https://github.com/schmidii/data_experiment), (10.5281/zenodo.2619280,10.5281/zenodo.2617382,10.5281/zenodo.2617376).

Specify what methods or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

To access the produced data for the raw data a normal text editor is enough because it's saved as csv file. Of cores it can be accessed by other suited programs as excel as well. The plots are saved as png image, therefore an image viewer is needed. All data should be easily accessible by mobile devices and notebooks.

To reproduce the data python3.7, jupyter notebook and some other libraries have to be installed. The list of libraries needed is in the requirements.txt in Git. Additionally, there is a docker file provided, which can be used to run the python file, in case docker is used only docker is needed.

Specify where the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited

The git folder structure is as follows

- * `data/raw` - Folder containing the external data
- * `data/processed` - Folder to store the results
- * `reports` - Folder to store the diagrams
- * `documentation/` - Folder to store metadata and other documentation
- * `/` Docker files, Requirements, python file, Readme

Specify how access will be provided in case there are any restrictions

There are no access restrictions.

2.3 Making data interoperable [FAIR data]

Assess the interoperability of your data. Specify what data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies you will follow to facilitate interoperability.

As described earlier all data produced and used as input can be opened with open source software from all different operating systems. The language used for the whole experiment is English which should also support the possibility to exchange the data.

Specify whether you will be using standard vocabulary for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability? If not, will you provide mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

All vocabulary used are standard vocabularies

2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses) [FAIR data]

Specify how the data will be licenced to permit the widest reuse possible

The most restricted licensed from the input datasets is cc-by-4.0, which allows reuse if the origin is named. Therefore, I will also publish my results under cc-by-4.0 to preserve the trackability. But don't have real constrains for reusing the results.

Specify when the data will be made available for re-use. If applicable, specify why and for what period a data embargo is needed

The data is already public available and therefore available for re-use. It has been made available immediately after producing it, via git and later with DOI's.

Specify whether the data produced and/or used in the project is useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why

Generally, there is neither on the input data nor on the produced data any restrictions.

The input data: "*Katalog Regionalisierte Bevölkerungsprognose*" is reusable for everyone if the originator is mentioned (Magistrat Vienna) it's published under cc-by-4.0

The input data: "*Population by age group*" is reusable by everyone, it doesn't have any restrictions.

The data produced is also published under cc-by-4.0 to have still the trackability to the magistrate Vienna. But this still means that everything can be used by other third parties

Describe data quality assurance processes

In the project there are two input data sets involved. Both get processed via python resulting in the end in comparable data. The exact steps are written in the Readme. In the end one of the datasets gets subtracted by the other and printed as a line chart. The whole project is hosted on GitHub which was used for versioning.

Specify the length of time for which the data will remain re-usable

The data will be reusable immediately, in git they are available since March 31. They will stay available till the end of the Semester and therefore the end of the lecture data stewardship for which they got produced. Afterwards they might still be online, but it won't get maintained anymore and therefore re-usability isn't guaranteed anymore.

3. Allocation of resources

Estimate the costs for making your data FAIR. Describe how you intend to cover these costs

There are no monetary costs to make the Data fair. To host the project on GitHub and get the different DOI's is free. The time to get DOI's and also creating the GitHub repository is to less to really count as costs.

Clearly identify responsibilities for data management in your project

Since I (David Schmidt) am the only one directly involved with the project, I am responsible for the data management.

Describe costs and potential value of long term preservation

There are no costs for long term preservation. The value for others includes the data as template for other students with similar exercises.

4. Data security

Address data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data

The data recovery is based on the availability of the input data, which I am not responsible for. Other data recovery aspects are the availability of the project as a whole I will assure that on GitHub and with DOI's till the end of the summer term 2019. Additionally, the data is stored on a local machine as backup.

The data doesn't contain any sensitive data therefore storage and transfer are less problematic.

5. Ethical aspects

To be covered in the context of the ethics review, ethics section of DoA and ethics deliverables. Include references and related technical aspects if not covered by the former

There are no legal or ethical aspects. The input data is publicly available for everyone and doesn't contain personal data. By the experiment the data is compared and processed further but, in the end, only abstraction is added and therefore I can still see no legal or ethical problems.

6. Other

Refer to other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management that you are using (if any)

There are no other procedures used for the data management.